

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: N'dri****FIRST NAME: Kouadio Jean****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1. In notes-bibliography style, elements are generally ordered as follows:

- Author, title, facts of publication.¹**
- Author, title, date, and facts of publication.
- Author, date, and facts of publication.
- Title, author, date, and facts of publication.

2. In the author-date style, edit into the parentheses:

- Author's first name commas and the page number.
- Author's last name date of publication commas, and page number.²**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 154.

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 239.

- Author's last name period, editor's first name, and publication date.
 - Author's last name commas, date of publication commas, page number.
3. Students and inexperienced writers may be charged with plagiarism when they:
- Quote, paraphrase, summarize, or use the exact words of a source but fail to cite it.
 - Use ideas or methods from a source and fail to cite them.
 - Paraphrase a source and cite it but paraphrase too closely.
 - All the above is correct.**³
4. What are the components of Dissertation Research?
- Dissertation concept Paper, Dissertation prospectus.
 - Dissertation concept Paper, Dissertation prospectus, Dissertation, Dissertation manuscript.**⁴
 - Dissertation manuscript, Dissertation prospectus, Dissertation.
 - Dissertation, Dissertation manuscript.
5. The following factors contribute to a successful Dissertation Research:
- Good communication, Good planning.
 - Using an effective process of writing and attention to detail.
 - Openness to serendipity, Visualizing success.

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 80.

⁴ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 9.

All the above is correct.⁵

6. Sources are conventionally categorized into:

Two kinds: primary and secondary

Three kinds: Primary, secondary, and tertiary.⁶

Four kinds: Primary, secondary, tertiary, and quarterly

Sources are not categorized at all.

7. According to the Manual of Turabian, the back matters of a thesis or dissertation are composed of:

Conclusion, Illustration, Appendix, Glossary, Endnotes.

Illustration, Appendix, Glossary, Endnotes, Reference list.⁷

Appendix, Acknowledgement, introduction, parts, Discussion.

Glossary, Endnotes, Results, Analysis, Conclusion.

8. To enter a single-author book in the reference list, respect the following order:

Author's First Name, Author's Last Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book:
Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.

⁵ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 22.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 36.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 423.

- Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. *Title of Book:*
Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.⁸**
- Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. (Year of Publication). Title of Book:
Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication.
- Author's Last Name, *Author's First Name*. Year of Publication. "Title of Book":
Subtitle of Book.

9. In reference list entries, separate most elements with:

- Semicolons,
- Periods,⁹**
- Commas,
- Question marks.

10. A reference list is arranged:

- Chronologically by the author's First name.
- Chronologically by the author's Last name.
- Alphabetically by the author's Last name.¹⁰**
- Alphabetically by the author's First name.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, 229.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 234.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 235.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2017.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.